

Force of Quantum Gravity

Between Two Bodies

Ravindra Sidramappa Mundase

23/11/2017

Consider two bodies A and B separated by distance r . Assume that body A is large solid sphere having radius R_s . Another body B is a point mass. Let M be the mass of Body A and m be the mass of body B. Consider a very thin a shell of A having radius R . Assume that thickness of shell is dR as shown in figure given below. Let σ be volume density of mass of a given shell shaped body A.

Figure : 1

Let dM be the mass of thin shell of A with thickness dR

$$dM = 4\pi R^2 \sigma dR$$

According to Shell theorem of quantum gravity, the quantum gravitational force dF_q of the thin shell of A on a point mass body B is given by ¹

$$\begin{aligned} dF_q &= \frac{G_s dM m}{r^2} + G_q dM m \left[1 - \frac{1}{3} \sin^2 \phi \right] \\ &= \frac{G_s 4\pi R^2 \sigma dR}{r^2} + G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma dR \left[1 - \frac{1}{3} \sin^2 \phi \right] \end{aligned}$$

The total quantum gravitational force of sphere A on body B can be calculated by integrating the above equation

$$\int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} dF_q = \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{G_s 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR}{r^2} + \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR \left(1 - \frac{1}{3} \sin^2 \emptyset \right)$$

$$\int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} dF_q = \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{G_s 4\pi R_0^2 \sigma m dR}{r^2} + \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR - \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{1}{3} \sin^2 \emptyset G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR$$

From figure 1 we know that

$$\tan^2 \emptyset = \frac{R^2}{r^2}$$

$$\int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} dF_q = \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{G_s 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR}{r^2} + \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR - \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{R^2}{r^2} \right) G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR$$

$$\int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} dF_q = \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{G_s 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR}{r^2} + \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} G_q 4\pi R^2 \sigma m dR - \int_{R=0}^{R=R_s} \frac{1}{3r^2} G_q 4\pi R^4 \sigma m dR$$

$$F_q = \frac{G_s 4\pi R_s^3 \sigma m}{3r^2} + \frac{G_q 4\pi R_s^3 \sigma m}{3} - \frac{G_q 4\pi \sigma m}{3r^2} \left(\frac{R_s^5}{5} \right)$$

We know that the mass M of solid sphere A is given by

$$M = \text{mass density of volume} \times \text{volume}$$

$$M = \sigma \times \frac{4\pi R_s^3}{3}$$

$$= \frac{4\sigma\pi R^3}{3}$$

$$F_q = \frac{G_s M m}{r^2} + \frac{G_q M m}{1} - \frac{G_q M m}{1} \left(\frac{R^2}{5r^2} \right)$$

$$F_q = \frac{G_s M m}{r^2} + G_q M m \left(1 - \frac{R^2}{5r^2} \right)$$

From figure 1 we know that

$$\sin^2 \emptyset = \frac{R_s^2}{r^2}$$

$$F_q = \frac{G_s M m}{r^2} + G_q M m \left(1 - \frac{1}{5} \sin^2 \emptyset \right)$$

References:

- 1) Ravindra Sidramappa Mundase: - Theory of Quantum Gravity
(zenodo.org, Publication date 10/02/2019, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo2561161)